

Joint Action on integrating prevention, testing and linkage to care strategies across HIV, viral hepatitis, TB and STIs in Europe

INTEGRATE partner survey

Baseline Data Report

July 2018

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1. Baseline Partner Survey - Methodology

Background

To plan and initiate the work in the four INTEGRATE work packages baseline survey information from the partners was needed. To facilitate this process, it was decided to make one comprehensive survey covering all work package areas. All work package leads formulated specific questions on their area of work, which were compiled and set up in the online data collection system redcap.

The survey was circulated among all INTEGRATE partners and collaborating stakeholders in November-December 2017.

Respondents

We have received 26 answers from partners, and 5 answers from collaborating stakeholders [N=31] (List of respondents in Annex D).

The 26 partners that responded to the survey are a diverse group ranging from smaller NGOs with under 5 staff members to large public health institutes or hospitals with several hundred employees. Most of the partners are from the eastern part of Europe (Lithuania, Estonia, Croatia, Hungary, Romania, Poland, Slovenia and Slovakia) and a minor part is from the Southern Europe (Italy, Spain, Greece and Malta) and Western Europe (Ireland). In addition, INTEGRATE has also partners in UK, Denmark and Serbia.

Analysis of responses

All WP leads have been given the data and each have analysed their relevant section to inform the work planning.

2. Prevention activities

2.1 Engagement in prevention activities

2.1.1 Does the organisation conduct prevention activities (across all or any of the conditions: HIV, viral, hepatitis, TB and STIs)

Among the respondents [N=29], 23 respondents (80%) answered that they conduct prevention activities and 5 respondents (17%) answered that they do not conduct prevention activities. 1 respondents (3%) answered “Don’t know”.

The prevention activities the organizations conduct are:

- educational workshops and one-to-one education during patient visits (UCD School of Medicine);
- anonymous and free of charge HIV testing (SMU);
- mobile clinics providing harm reduction services (RCAD);
- general promotion for sexual and reproductive health (NIJZ);
- needle exchange and prevention activities as a part of PEP consultations (FLIGHT)
- conducts prevention activities in collaboration with direction for public health (CHIDPVB)

Regarding prevention activities, most of the activities target youth, MSM, PWID and sex workers. Other kind of key populations the respondents mentioned [N=7] were 50+ and pregnant women in the general population, all people who would like to be tested and medical staffs who are exposed to TB (see table 14).

Table 1: Key populations in the prevention [N=21]

KEY POPULATION	COUNTS/FREQUENCY
MSM	15 (71 %)
PWID	13 (62 %)
Sex workers	11 (52 %)
Migrants	8 (38 %)
Homeless people	6 (29 %)
Youth	14 (67 %)
Transgender	5 (24 %)
Others	8 (38 %)

2.2 Use of ICT Tools

Most of the organization use social networks, emails and ICT to disseminate information to clients as an information communication tool in the organisation. Among the respondents who answered “Other”, one answered that they use AIDS Helpline as an information communication tool (see Table 15).

Table 2: Information communication technology (ICT) tools used in the organization [N=22]

KEY POPULATION	COUNTS/FREQUENCY
ICT to collect information from clients	7 (32 %)
ICT to disseminate information to clients	10 (46 %)
Link virtual content to physical services (e.g. adds to private for-profit platforms)	4 (18 %)
Enhance compliance (reminders via email, apps or text messages)	5 (23 %)
Partner notification or contact tracing (via email, apps or text messages)	2 (9 %)
Mobile apps	5 (23 %)
Social networks	15 (68 %)
E-mail	12 (55 %)
Online courses/e-learning	7 (32 %)
Other	6 (27 %)

2.3 Partner notification/contact tracing

2.3.1 In the organisation what are the current practices around partner notification for these diseases?

In terms of partner notification it is clear that most of the respondents don't do partner notifications for HIV, hepatitis B & C, STIs and TB. However, some respondents answered that they do patient referral where patients contact their partners directly, especially for HIV, hepatitis and TB (see Table 16).

Table 3: Current practices around partner notification for HIV, hepatitis B/C, STIs and TB

CURRENT PRACTICES	HIV	HEPATITIS B & C	STIs	TB
We don't do partner notification for [N=18]	15 (83 %)	16 (89 %)	16 (89 %)	12 (67 %)

Passive contact tracing via post or email [N=6]	4 (67 %)	2 (33 %)	4 (67 %)	1 (17 %)
Active contact tracing e.g. via home visits [N=8]	1 (13 %)	1 (13 %)	1 (13 %)	6 (75 %)
Healthcare assisted contact tracing [N=9]	5 (56 %)	3 (33 %)	5 (56 %)	8 (89 %)
Community assisted contact tracing [N=6]	2 (33 %)	2 (33 %)	-	4 (67 %)
Patient referral (patients contact their partners directly) [N=12]	10 (83 %)	8 (67 %)	6 (50 %)	8 (67 %)
Provider referral (health providers contact partners on patients' behalf) [N=4]	2 (50 %)	2 (50 %)	3 (75 %)	4 (100 %)
Anonymous notification via email, text messaging, etc. [N=2]	2 (100 %)	1 (50 %)	2 (100 %)	-

Staffs who most commonly are assigned to partner notification are doctors. Also nurses are usual assigned to partner notification. One respondent answered "Others" and mentioned that public health doctors are assigned to partner notification (see Table 17).

Table 4: What staffs are assigned to partner notification? [N=14]

STAFF	COUNTS/FREQUENCY
Doctors	10 (71 %)
Nurses	8 (57 %)
Councillors	6 (43 %)
Peers	3 (21 %)
Others	1 (7 %)

2.3.2 What barriers/difficulties does the organisation perceive in the partner notification of the organisation?

Among the respondents [N=10], two organisations mentioned lack of patient education as a barrier the organisation perceive in the partner notification of the organisation. One respondent answered that the patients' inaccurate sexual history (e.g. do not know who infected him/her or do not want to tell it) is a barrier and another respondent answered that the shortage of personnel, lack of interest and guidance from national surveillance are barriers the organisation perceive in the partner notification of the organisation.

Most of the respondents think that all the mentioned measures are needed to improve the partner notification of the organisations. Three respondents answered “Other” and mentioned that additional time given to health care professionals for PN/CT and setting a surveillance system, which should provide assistance and resources are needed (see Table 18).

Table 5: Measures which would needed to improve the partner notification of the organisation [N=14]

MEASURES	COUNTS/FREQUENCY
Share of experiences with other countries	10 (71 %)
National guidelines	10 (71 %)
Training for health care providers	10 (71 %)
Training for CBVCT staff	10 (71 %)
Other	3 (21 %)

2.3.3 National Level Prevention Activities

Partner notification/contact tracing is mandatory for HIV in Romania and Hungary, for hepatitis B in Slovakia and Hungary, for Hepatitis C in Slovakia, for Chlamydia in Slovakia and Hungary, for Gonorrhoea in Slovakia and Hungary and for TB in Ireland, Slovakia, Croatia, Slovenia and Hungary. Partner notification/contract tracing is not mandatory for HIV in Ireland, Poland, Croatia, Slovakia, Lithuania, Latvia and Slovenia, for hepatitis C in Ireland, Poland, Croatia, Lithuania, Latvia, Slovenia and Hungary, for hepatitis B, syphilis, chlamydia and gonorrhoea in Ireland, Poland, Croatia, Lithuania, Latvia and Slovenia, and for TB in Poland, Croatia and Latvia. For some of the conditions, the respondents did not know about it (see table 19).

Table 6: Mandatory partner notification/contact tracing for HIV, Hepatitis B/C, syphilis, chlamydia, gonorrhoea and TB

COUNTRY (PARTNER)	HIV	HEPATITIS B	HEPATITIS C	SYPHILIS	CHLAMYDIA	GONORRHOEA	TB
Ireland (UCD School of Medicine)	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
Poland (NAC)	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Croatia (HUHIV)	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Slovakia (SMU)	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Lithuania (RCAD)	No	No	No	No	No	No	Don't know

Romania (IPMN)	Yes	Don't know	Yes				
Latvia (NV SPL)	No						
Romania (CHIDPVB)	Yes	Don't know	Yes				
Slovenia (NIJZ)	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
Greece (CERTH)	Don't know						
Croatia (FLIGHT)	No	Don't know					
Poland (WUM)	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	No
Hungary(MoH)	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Most of the respondents answered that there are no legal required partner notification/contract tracing in their country on HIV, hepatitis B, hepatitis C, syphilis, chlamydia, gonorrhoea and TB or that they do not know about it.

The table shows that there is legal required reporting on partner notification/contract tracing on TB in Ireland, Slovakia, Romania, and Hungary, where there is no legal required reporting in Poland, Croatia, Lithuania and Greece. Among the respondents, only two countries have legal required reporting on partner notification/contract tracing on chlamydia (Slovakia and Hungary), gonorrhoea (Slovakia and Hungary), HIV (Croatia and Hungary) and hepatitis B (Slovakia, Hungary). Additionally, three countries (Hungary, Poland and Slovakia) have legal required reporting on partner notification/contact tracing on syphilis and only one country (Slovakia) have on hepatitis C. A lot of the respondents answered that they do not know about it.

Of all the disease areas, responses to TB contact tracing appeared to be the most comprehensive and understood, with participants often identifying guidelines, documents or outlining the national procedures involved in contact tracing. Many partners noted that often guidelines for partner notification for HIV and STIs are combined (see table 20).

Table 7: Legal required reporting on partner notification/contact tracing

COUNTRY (PARTNER)	HIV	HEPATITIS B	HEPATITIS C	SYPHILIS	CHLAMYDIA	GONORRHOEA	TB
Ireland (UCD School of Medicine)	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
Poland (NAC)	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Croatia (HUHIV)	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Slovakia (SMU)	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Lithuania (RCAD)	No	No	No	No	No	No	Don't know
Romania (IPMN)	Yes	Don't know	Yes				
Latvia (NV SPL)	No						
Romania (CHIDPVB)	Yes	Don't know	Yes				
Slovenia (NIJZ)	No	No	No	No	No	No	Don't know
Greece (HCDCP (KEELPNO))	No						
Greece (CERTH)	Don't know						
Croatia (FLIGHT)	Don't know						
Poland (WUM)	No	No		Yes	No	No	No
Hungary (MoH)	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Partner notification/contact tracing is most done by health care assisted PN/contact tracing for all conditions. The respondents who answered "Other" reported that it is done by patient referral and counselling of index patient to notify contacts. One respondent reported that they don't have any formal existing regulations (see table 21).

Table 8: How partner notification/contact tracing is done

METHODS	HIV (N=19)	HEPATITIS B (N=14)	HEPATITIS C (N=14)	SYHILIS (N=18)	CHLAMYDIA (N=16)	GONORRHOEA (N=17)	TB (N=17)
Passive PN/contact tracing via post or email	4 (21 %)	4 (29 %)	4 (29 %)	4 (22 %)	4 (25 %)	4 (27 %)	2 (12 %)
Active PN/contact tracing e.g. via home visits	4 (21 %)	4 (29 %)	2 (14 %)	3 (17 %)	2 (16 %)	2 (12 %)	8 (47 %)
Health care assisted PN/contact tracing	12 (63 %)	8 (57 %)	8 (57 %)	12 (67 %)	11 (69 %)	12 (71 %)	13 (77 %)
Community assisted PN/contact tracing	4 (21 %)	2 (14 %)	3 (21 %)	2 (11 %)	1 (6 %)	1 (6 %)	4 (24 %)

Other	6 (32 %)	4 (29 %)	3 (21 %)	5 (28 %)	5 (31 %)	5 (29 %)	3 (18 %)
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As demonstrated by the first Integrate partner survey, there appears to be significant levels of confusion and/or uncertainty surrounding the partner notification laws, regulations and practices. This is evidenced in multiple ways: conflicting responses given by respondents from the same country, a high amount of unanswered questions, many questions answered with 'don't know', few best practice examples of partner notification, and few links/ attachments to country guidelines on partner notification/ contact tracing. It is important to note that these findings do not necessarily indicate that partner notification does not occur, particularly as the respondents could be answering from the point of view of their particular organization instead of the host country's operating procedures. Instead, they do point to a lack of knowledge/ understanding of how/if partner notification does or does not occur within these contexts (see table 22).

Table 9: Guidelines for partner notification/contact tracing in the country

COUNTRY (PARTNER)	HIV	HEPATITIS B	HEPATITIS C	SYPHILIS	CHLAMYDIA	GONORRHOEA	TB	LINKS AND CONTACTS
Ireland (UCD School of Medicine)	No	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	http://www.hpsc.ie/a-z/vaccinepreventable/tuberculosis/tb/guidance/ , for STIs Ireland would follow BASHH guidelines
Poland (NAC)	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	
Croatia (HUHIV)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	For guidelines contact Croatian institute for public health - https://www.hzjz.hr/en/
Slovakia (SMU)	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Lithuania (RCAD)	Don't know	Don't know	Don't know	Don't know	Don't know	Don't know	Don't know	
Romania (IPMN)	Yes	Don't know	Don't know	Don't know	Don't know	Don't know	Yes	http://srp.ro/ghiduri/Ghid_pt%20BT.pdf National Directorate of Public Health, Ministry of Health, National Institute of Public Health
Latvia (NVSPL)	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	

Romania (CHIDPVB)	Don't know	Yes	http://www.srp.ro/ghiduri/Ghid_pt%20BT.pdf DIRECTION FOR PUBLIC HEALTH, NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF PUBLIC HEALTH					
Slovenia (NIJZ)	No	No	No	No	No	No	Don't know	For TB: petra.svetina-sorli@klinika-golnik.si
Greece (HCDCP (KEELPNO))	Yes	No	No				No	
Greece (CERTH)	Don't know							
Croatia (FLIGHT)	No	Don't know						
Poland (WUM)	No							

Despite a lack of in-depth knowledge of how partner notification occurs, respondents were able to identify numerous barriers and challenges that impede the process. These include limited resources, limited time, limited staff, lack of guidelines, lack of patient education, confidentiality issues and stigma (see table 23).

Table 10: Main challenges for carrying out partner notification/contact tracing

CHALLENGES	HIV (N=19)	HEPATITIS B (N=17)	HEPATITIS C (N=17)	SYHILIS (N=19)	CHLAMYDIA (N=19)	GONORRHOEA (N=19)	TB (N=19)
Limited resources	9 (47 %)	8 (47 %)	8 (47 %)	10 (53 %)	10 (53 %)	9 (47 %)	5 (26 %)
Limited time	7 (37 %)	7 (41 %)	7 (41 %)	8 (42 %)	9 (47 %)	8 (42 %)	5 (26 %)
Limited staff	10 (53 %)	9 (53 %)	9 (53 %)	11 (58 %)	11 (58 %)	11 (58 %)	13 (68 %)
Lack of guidelines	10 (53 %)	10 (59 %)	10 (59 %)	8 (42 %)	8 (42 %)	8 (42 %)	6 (32 %)
No routines in place	8 (42 %)	7 (41 %)	8 (47 %)	10 (53 %)	10 (53 %)	11 (58 %)	6 (32 %)
Other	3 (16 %)	1 (6 %)	1 (6 %)	3 (16 %)	3 (16 %)	3 (16 %)	3 (16 %)

2.3.4 In your country, are you aware of any recent changes in the legal requirements for partner notification for HIV/hepatitis/STIs (after 2012)

Among the respondents [N=24], 3 respondents (13 %) answered that they are aware of recent changes in legal requirements for partner notification for HIV, hepatitis and/or STIs and 12 respondents (50 %) answered that they are not aware of it. 9 respondents (37 %) answered that they do not know and referred to persons/institutions who know more about it (<http://www.mz.gov.pl/>; <https://www.hzjz.hr/en/>; assoc. prof. Mária Avdičova avdicova@vzbb.sk Dr. Peter Truska, PhD ba.truska@uvzs.sk; National Directorate for Public Health; DIRECTION FOR PUBLIC HEALTH, NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF PUBLIC HEALTH).

Table 11: Who is responsible for carrying out TB contact tracing? Are public health departments involved? Is there a mandatory reporting mechanism?

PARTNER	RESPONSIBLE FOR CARRYING OUT TB CONTACT TRACING	PUBLIC HEALTH DEPARTMENT	MANDATORY REPORTING MECHANISM
Hospital Clinic-IDIBAPS	Infectious Disease Department from Hospital Clinic of Barcelona-IDIBAPS		
UCD School of Medicine		Public health department would take over the duties of contact tracing after the instance is reported. They have doctors dedicated to contact tracing and report contacts in local departments	
NAC	Please contact: http://www.igichp.edu.pl/		
HUHIV	There are guidelines from Croatian institute for public health - https://www.hzjz.hr/en/		
SMU		National Institute of Tuberculosis and Pulmonary Diseases in Vysne Hagy in the cooperation with phthisiologists and epidemiologists from the Institute of Public Health	
Republican Center for Addictive Disorders (RCAD)		Probably the municipalities (local/regional government) should organize the work or	

		delegate other institutions to do it.	
IPMN	Community nurses	Local public health department is involved	A mandatory reporting mechanism is in place for outbreaks
NVSLP	Treating Physician		
IPMN	Family doctor, pulmonologist	In cases of disease outbreak, the epidemiologist in the public Health Department is involved	
CHIDPVB	Community nurses	PUBLIC HEALTH DIRECTION INVOLVED	
NIJZ	University Hospital for Pulmonary Diseases- Golnik		
HELLENIC CENTER FOR DISEASE CONTROL & PREVENTION		Public Health authorities	
WUM	National TB Institute, but there is no passive or active contact tracing		
MoH	Contact tracing is carried out by pulmonology	Public health departments not involved	There is mandatory reporting mechanism

3. Training needs

3.1.1 Monitoring of testing and linkage to care

To improve the monitoring of testing and linkage to care in the organizations, the respondents identify different needs. Some of them identify a need for improving sharing of information between the organizations and clinics; define standards for reporting and training in appropriate IT tools and research methods. Others have a need for training in how to explain the different health care providers' clinical pathways of newly infected HIV patients, and training in how to monitor treatment and tracking of patients. One respondent (HPDP) indicates that the presence of more cultural mediators will improve monitoring of testing and linkage to care. Lastly, some report that the training should focus on patient motivation, learning in how to work in teams with different specialists and to use the best practice models implemented in other countries.

However, some of the respondents did not see a need for training, but instead a need for more resources (economic and human) to do the tasks and for the national stakeholders to understand the needs.

3.1.2 Combination prevention with ICT tools and Partner Notification

17 respondents answered the question about in which areas the organisation would benefit the most from training on combination prevention with ICT tools. The areas they mentioned were: patient resources (UCD School of Medicine); partner notification (HUHIV); collect information, disseminate information and enhance compliance (CHIDPVB); mobile apps (NIJZ); training in health care professionals in AIDS related issues, testing as well as in counselling, raise public awareness, eliminate stigma, provide sensitization and educate about sexual and reproductive health issues (HCDPC). Two respondents (NAC and RCAD) answered that they could benefit from all areas.

Regarding partner notification, respondents noted that in order to improve PN/CT efforts, there is a need for more training of healthcare providers and CBVCT staff, introducing national guidelines on PN/CT and sharing experiences of PN/CT with other countries.

Annex A

Table 12: Contact Information, surveys and cohorts

COUNTRY (PARTNER)	PLHIV SURVEYS/EVALUATIONS	HEPATITIS C PATIENTS SURVEYS/EVALUATIONS	COHORTS HIV/HEPATITIS C
Ireland (UCD)	Stigma related questionnaires; HIV Ireland (www.hivireland.ie); Nick Quinlan, Niall Mulligan	n.a	n.a.
Poland (NAC)	GARP always contains a community section and it is filled in by a HIV+ activist; A survey conducted in the framework of HA-REACT project in 2016;	Contact: http://www.gwiazdanadziei.pl	n.a.
Croatia (HUHIV)	The only research that we are aware of is what we have been doing within our project 'Aging with HIV' among people living with HIV during 2017. The study included PLHIV from Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro and Macedonia; https://huhiv.hr/ ; Maja Erceg, mag.psych. psychologist at Croatian association for HIV and viral hepatitis; HUHIV has been conducting client perspective evaluation in Check Point Zagreb (2015, 2016), results are in HIVhep year book for medical workers	HUHIV has been conducting client perspective evaluation in Check Point Zagreb (2015, 2016), results are in HIVhep year book for medical workers (https://huhiv.hr/hivhep-godisnjak/)	n.a.
Romania (IPMN)	Quality of life questionnaires, adherence surveys; National Anti AIDS Commission; www.cnlas.ro ; www.raa.ro	APAH- APAH RO; Marinela Debu, www.hepato.ro ; www.raa.ro	Matei Bals Institute www.cnlas.ro
Romania (CHIDPVB)	quality of life, adherence questionnaires; quality of life, adherence questionnaires	PATIENTS ORGANISATION	n.a.

Spain (CEEISCAT)	Yes; Julia del Amo	n.a.	At regional level (Catalonia) : PISCIS Cohort http://www.pisciscohort.org/ PI: Dr. Jordi Casabona At national level: CORIS Cohort Coordination: Centro Nacional de Epidemiología (Instituto de Salud Carlos III)
Slovenia (NIJZ)	Phd thesis LAMUT, Aleš. Kulturno antropološki in epidemiološki vidiki spolnih praks istospolno usmerjenih moških v Sloveniji v obdobju porasta spolno prenosljivih okužb : doktorska disertacija. Ljubljana: [A. Lamut], 2013.; LAMUT, Aleš	Contact: Andrej Kastelic and Mojca Matičič (University Medical Centre Ljubljana)	Contact: Mojca Matičič (University Medical Centre Ljubljana)
Greece (HCDCP (KEELPNO))	Contact: AMASE	n.a.	AMACS
Serbia (IPH)	Last survey on Quality of life among PLHIV in Serbia has been conducted in 2013; The report is available only in Serbian on web site of IPH of Serbia (look at under publication)	n.a.	n.a.
Croatia (FLIGHT)	Yes; University Hospital For Infectious Diseases	RDS study among PWID in Zagreb, Rijeka and Split (2014/2015); Governmental Office For Drug Suppression www.drogeovisnosti.gov.hr	n.a.
Poland (WUM)	Magdalena Ankiersztejn-Bartczak (FES); megama@poczta.onet.pl	n.a.	Polish Observational Cohort of HIV/AIDS Patients
Slovakia	n.a.	Contact: prof. L. Skladany,	

(SMU)		lubomir.skladany@gmail.com	
Spain (Hospital Clinic- IDIBAPS)	Contact: Laia Cayuelas, Ignacio Menacho, Agathe Leon	n.a.	CoRIS
Lithuania (RPLC)	n.a.	n.a.	www.ulac.lt

Table 13: Information provided from outside the organisation

PARTNER	IINFORMATION
UCD School of Medicine	Discussed with HPSC members for information
SMU	Assoc. prof. Mária Avdičova avdicova@vzbb.sk Dr. Peter Truska, PhD
HELLENIC CENTER FOR DISEASE CONTROL & PREVENTION	OKANA (Organisation against drugs)
FLIGHT	Croatian National Public Health Institute
WUM	http://www.igichp.edu.pl/

Annex B

Table 14: Description of where in the healthcare system patients with STIs typically present (includes next most common place as well)

COUNTRY (Partners)	PTs WITH STIs	PTs WITH HEPATITIS B/C VIRUS	PTs WITH MONONUCLEOSIS-LIKE ILLNESS	PTs WITH PNEUMONIA	HERPES ZOSTER	MALIGNANT LYMPHOMA	CERVICAL/ANAL CANCERS/DYSPLASIA	TB
Spain (Hospital Clinic-IDIBAPS)	At STI specialized care facilities	Acute hepatitis in emergency departments and general care providers chronic hepatitis found out by screening newly diagnosed or at the normal follow up of HIV infected patients	General providers Emergency departments	General providers Emergency departments	General providers Emergency departments	General providers Emergency departments	General providers Emergency departments STI clinics routine visits to the gynaecologists	General providers Emergency departments
Ireland (UCD)	Public health clinics, private GP practice	Public health clinics, private GP practice, drug treatment centres	GP practice, ER	GP practices, emergency rooms	GP practices, emergency rooms	Haematologists, cancer doctors	STD clinics, GP practices, gynaecologists	ID specialists, respiratory specialists, ER
Poland (NAC)	Dermatologists	http://www.gwia-zdanadziei.pl/		http://www.igichp.edu.pl/			http://www.coi.pl/	http://www.igichp.edu.pl/

Croatia (HUHIV)	General Practitioner, Gynaecologist, Private Clinics	Clinic for infectious diseases in Zagreb and other hepatic medicine office in local hospitals.	Clinic for infectious diseases in Zagreb and General Practitioners	Clinic for infectious diseases in Zagreb and General Practitioners	Clinic for infectious diseases in Zagreb and General Practitioners	Clinic for infectious diseases in Zagreb and General Practitioners and other hospitals	Clinic for infectious diseases in Zagreb and General Practitioners and other hospitals	Clinic for infectious diseases in Zagreb and General Practitioners and other hospitals and clinical centres.
Slovakia (SMU)	In clinics of dermatovenerology	Clinics of infectology, departments of hepatology	Clinics of infectology	Departments of pneumology	Clinics of infectology	Institutes or departments of oncology	Special oncological ambulances or institutes or departments of oncology	Institute of tuberculosis and respiratory diseases
Lithuania (RCAD [RPLC])	At Demetra and at primary healthcare level.	Primary healthcare level	Primary healthcare level	Primary healthcare level	Primary and tertiary healthcare level	Primary healthcare level	Probably primary healthcare level	Probably primary healthcare level
Romania (IPMN)	Dermatologist, Gynaecologist, Family doctor	Gastro-enterologist, infectious disease specialist, family doctor	Pulmonologist, family doctor, infectious disease specialist	Pulmonologist, family doctor.	Dermatologist, family doctor, infectious disease	Family doctor, pulmonologist, haematologist	Gynaecologist, family doctor, surgeon	Family doctor, pulmonologist
Latvia (NVSPL)	Government institution (laboratories, hospitals) and private clinics, laboratories.	Government institution (laboratories, hospitals) and private clinics, laboratories	Government institution (laboratories, hospitals).	Government institution (laboratories, hospitals) and private clinics, laboratories.	Government institution (laboratories, hospitals) and private clinics, laboratories	Government institution (laboratories, hospitals).	Government institution (laboratories, hospitals).	Government institution (laboratories, hospitals).

Romania (IPMN)	Derma, boli inf.	b. inf., gastro	b. inf	med, fam, med. internal, pneumo	derma	Pneumo., chir.	chir, gastro	med, fam, penumo, disp TBC
Romania (CHIDPVB)	DERMATOLOGIST, FAMILY DOCTOR, GYNECOLOGIST	FAMILY DOCTOR, GASTROENTEROLOGY, INFECTIOUS DISEASES	FAMILY DOCTOR, INFECTIOUS DISEASES, PNEUMOLOGIST, HAEMATOLOGIST	FAMILY DOCTOR, INFECTIOUS DISEASES, PNEUMOLOGIST	INFECTIOUS DISEASES, DERMATOLOGIST, FAMILY DOCTOR	FAMILY DOCTOR, HAEMATOLOGIST	GYNECOLOGIST, FAMILY DOCTOR, SURGEON	PNEUMOLOGIST, FAMILY DOCTOR, INFECTIOUS DISEASES
Slovenia (NIJZ)	General practice and STI outpatient services.	General practice and Infectious diseases departments in acute care hospitals.	General practice and Infectious diseases departments in acute care hospitals.	General practice and Infectious diseases departments in acute care hospitals.	General practice and Infectious diseases departments in acute care hospitals.	General practice and Oncology departments in acute care hospitals.	General practice/ gynaecologist at primary health care level, gynaecologist departments in acute care hospitals and gastroenterology-surgery.	General practice and University Hospital for Pulmonary Diseases- Golnik
Greece (HCDCP (KEELPNO))	Public hospitals, STI clinics	Public & private hospitals						Primary health care Services, hospitals both in public and private sector
Hungary (MoH)	Dermatology, Gynaecology	Infectology	Infectology or Internal medicine	Internal medicine	Infectology	Haematology	Cervical cancer: Gynecology Anal cancer: Surgery and Oncology	Pulmonology
Poland	Dermatology/STI HIV clinics for HIV+ gynaecologists for	Infectious diseases	GPs infectious diseases hospitals	GPs internal	GPs	Oncology/hematol	Gynecology	TB hospitals infectious

(WUM)	women but very poor acceptance from doctors	gastroenterology /hepatology internal medicine	general hospitals ENT	medicine		ogy		diseases hospitals
Italy (ARCIGAY)	<p>It depends on each of the 20 Italian regions.</p> <p>Every region has its own organization. In some country regions there are STI services including most of the STI testing activity, while in some other regions (and cities) there are different services for different STIs, depending also on the traditional specialty division followed in that area (for example, HIV and hepatitis in the infectious disease services, while syphilis, Gonorrhoea and chlamydia in dermatology services)</p>	<p>To the infectious diseases services in the or hospitals. The same working on HIV.</p>						<p>To the infectious diseases or tropical medicine</p> <p>The same working on HIV.</p>

Regarding the question whether the countries have national speciality guidelines for each listed condition, the respondents' show diverging knowledge (see Table 27).

Table 15: Does your country have national speciality guidelines for these conditions?

CONDITION	YES	NO	Don't know
STIs (N=29)	19 (66%)	7 (24%)	3 (10%)
Hepatitis B or C (acute or chronic) (N=29)	22 (76%)	3 (10%)	4 (14%)
Pneumonia (N=29)	13 (45%)	6 (24%)	9 (31%)
Herpes Zoster (N=27)	5 (19%)	8 (30%)	14 (52%)
Malignant lymphoma (N=27)	11 (41%)	3 (11%)	13 (48%)
Cervical or anal cancer/dysplasia (N=26)	12 (46%)	4 (15%)	10 (39%)
TB (N=29)	24 (83%)	1 (3%)	4 (14%)

Some respondents have provided links to the national specialty guidelines (see annex C)

Annex C - Links to National Speciality Guidelines

Table 16: Links to National Speciality Guidelines

PARTNERS	STI GUIDELINES	PNEUMONIA GUIDELINES	HERPES ZOSTER	MALIGNANT LYMPHOMA	CERVICAL/ANAL CANCER/DYSPLASIA	TB	OTHER
UCD School of Medicine	www.hpsc.ie	www.hpsc.ie				http://www.hpsc.ie/a-z/vaccinepreventable/tuberculosis/tb/guidance/	
SMU	http://www.technicka.sk/files/zakon-103-2015-rozvoji-verejneho-zdravia.pdf	http://www.uvzsr.sk/docs/info/epida/Zasady_na_vykonavanie_priotiep_opatreni_v_ohniskach_hepatitid.pdf		http://www.hivaidy.sk/index.php/novinky-zo-sveta/245-odborne-usmernenie-prevencia-hiv-infekcie-v-sr		http://www.nczisk.sk/Registre/Narodne-zdravotne-registre/Pages/Narodny-register-pacientov-s-tuberkulozou.aspx	Dr. Truska, p.truska@hotmail.com , prof. Audicova avdicova@vzbb.sk
IPMN	https://lege5.ro/Gratuit/gm3tsmrvgm/ordinul-nr-1342-2013-pentru-aprobarea-metodologiei-de-supraveghere-a-infectiilor-cu-transmitere-sexuala , http://srp.ro/ghiduri/Ghid_pt%20BT.pdf	www.mateibals.ro					

NVSPL	http://www.ulac.lt/uploads/downloads/leidiniai/9%20-%20LPI%20metodines.pdf	http://www.vlk.lt/veikla/veiklosritys/kompensuojamieji-vaistai/Documents/0128%20SAM%20C%20hepatitas%20V-960_RedakcijaNr_3.pdf	http://www.hi.lt/uploads/pdf/leidiniai/Rekomendacijos/Hospitaliniu_infekciju_prevencijos_rekomendacijos.pdf			https://www.e-tar.lt/portal/lt/legalAct/31481da0442411e6bd3bfe575ccac4	
IPMN		APH RO, Matei Bals		Societate derma, societate B inf	Chirurgie gastro - diag, onco - trat		
CHIDPVB	http://www.lex.ro/Ordin-1342-2013-130520.aspx					http://www.srp.ro/ghiduri/Ghid_pt%20BT.pdf	http://www.cnlas.ro
Slovenia (NIJZ)			Tatjana Lejko Zupanc (University Medical Centre Ljubljana)	Tatjana Lejko Zupanc, University Medical Centre Ljubljana	zora.onko-i.si/	no link	
Croatia (FLIGHT)	Croatian National Public Health Institute	www.hzjz.hr					
Hungary (MoH)	http://www.hbcs.hu/uploads/jogszabaly/2259/fajlok/szakmai_iranyelv_TBC.pdf						
Italy (ARCIGAY)		http://www.webaisf.org/media/36572/raccomandazioni_hbv		http://www.simit.org/IT/formazione/linee-guida.xhtml (massimo			

Annex D: List of Respondents:

Table 17: List of respondents

Record ID	Respondent/ Institution	Partner
25	1. Infectious Disease Department from Hospital Clinic of Barcelona-IDIBAPS	Hospital Clinic-IDIBAPS - Hospital (Spain)
29	2. Shannon Glaspy	UCD School of Medicine - University (Ireland)
38	3. Nadia Gasbarrini	FVM – drug rehabilitation centre (Italy)
40	4. Iwona Wawer	NAC - Agency of the Ministry of Health (Poland)
42	5. Arian Diskovic	HUHIV – NGO (Croatia)
51	6. Danica Staneková	SMU – University (Slovakia)
53	7. Gergő Merész	SU – University (Hungary)
55	8. Republican Center for Addictive Disorders	RCAD [RPLC] – support centre for drug addictive (Lithuania)
60	9. Raimonda Matulionyte	VULSK – University hospital (Lithuania)
61	10. Tatjana Nemeth Blažić	CIPH – Institute of Public Health (Croatia)
63	11. Ghita Eugenia	IPMN – Tuberculosis institute (Romania)

64	12. Ilona Kusleviciute	NVSPL – laboratory test (Lithuania)
65	13. Ghita Eugenia	IPMN
66	14. Lella Cosmaro	LILA Milano – NGO (Italy)
68	15. Antonella Sammut	HPDP (MFH Malta) – advocacy (Malta)
71	16. GRECU VICTOR IONEL	CHIDPVB – hospital (Romania)
72	17. Laura Fernández López	CEEISCAT – government agency (Spain – Catalonia)
73	18. Irena Klavs	NIJZ (National Institute of Public Health) (Slovenia)
74	19. Zoran Dominkovic	Iskorak – civil rights organization (Croatia)
75	20. Tervise Arengu Instituut (National Institute for Health Development)	TAI (NIHD) – government agency research (Estonia)
78	21. Irma Caplinskiene, MD	ULAC – governmental institution (Lithuania)
79	22. HELLENIC CENTER FOR DISEASE CONTROL & PREVENTION	HCDPC (KEELPNO) – private law entity (Greece)
80	23. Vassilis Koutkias	CERTH – research centre (Greece)
81	24. Danijela Simic	IPH – institute of public health (Serbia)
82	25. Iva Jovovic	FLIGHT – NGO

		(Croatia)
83	26. ARCIGAY	ARCIGAY – NGO (Italy)
	Collaborating	
9	27. Justyna Kowalska	WUM
23	28. Daniel Simões	GAT
67	29. Rossie G. Lugo	CEEISCAT
77+76 + 44	30. Dr. Agnes Galgóczi	MoH
48	31. Karl Kristian Bekeng	Helsedirektoratet

Annex E The Survey Form (empty PDF)

Consortium

Croatia

Hrvatski zavod za javno
zdravstvo Croatian Institute
of Public Health
Life Quality Improvement Association

Croatian association for HIV and viral
hepatitis

ISKORAK

Denmark

Region Hovedstaden / CHIP

Estonia

Tervise Arengu Instituut
National Institute for
Health Development

Greece

Centre for Research & Technology
Hellas, Institute of Applied
Biosciences, Information
Technologies institute

Hellenic Center for
Disease Control &
Prevention

Hungary

Semmelweis
University

Ireland

University College Dublin,
National university of
Ireland Dublin

Italy

Arcigay Associazione LGBTI

Croce Rossa Italiana

Fondazione LILA Milano ONLUS -
Lega Italiana per la Lotta contro l'AIDS

Fondazione Villa Maraini Onlus

Lithuania

National Public
Health Surveillance
Laboratory

REPUBLICAN
CENTRE FOR ADDICTIVE
DISORDERS

Republican Centre
for Addictive
Disorders

Centre for Communicable
Diseases
and AIDS

Vilnius University
Hospital Santaros Klinikos

Malta

Health Promotion and
Disease Prevention

Poland

National AIDS Centre
Agency of the Ministry of
Health

Romania

"Victor Babes" Clinical Hospital
of Infectious Diseases and
Pneumophtisiology Craiova

"Marius Nasta"
Pneumophtisiology Institute

INSTITUTE OF PUBLIC HEALTH OF SERBIA
"Dr Milan Jovanovic Batut"

Institute of Public Health
of Serbia "Dr Milan
Jovanovic Batut"

Slovakia

Slovak Medical University in
Bratislava

Slovenia

National Institute of
Public Health Nacionalni
inštitut za javno zdravje

Spain

Centre d'Estudis
Epidemiològics sobre les
ITS i Sida de Catalunya

Consorci Institut
d'Investigacions Biomèdicas
August Pi i Sunyer

Instituto de salud pública y laboral
de Navarra

United Kingdom

Public Health England